

WG3 Workshop “Citizen Science in Social Sciences and Humanities”

Date: June, 6th 2018

Location: University of Geneva, COST Citizen Science Workshopday

Participants:

Egle Butkeviciene, Dario Martinelli, Katrin Vohland, Loreta Tauginiene, Reidun Norvoll, Balint Balazs, Barbara Heinisch, Francesca De Chiara, Nora Salas Seoane, Carlos Canas, Johan Barstad, Hannah Stockwell, Maryam Lotfian, Baiba Prūse, Sieber Andrea.

Statistics:

15 participants (11 female and 4 male); the workshop included participants from 11 countries: Lithuania, Latvia, Norway, Austria, Italy, Spain, Malta, UK, Switzerland, Hungary, Germany.

Programme | Wednesday, June 6 (10:45 – 12:00)

- Introducing our experience to each other: short introductions of workshop participants and their short presentations about the experience regarding CS initiatives / expectations from the workshop (all participants)
- A brief presentation introducing results of previous workshop (Egle Butkeviciene)
- Citizen science & social sciences (Egle Butkeviciene)
- Citizen science & humanities (Dario Martinelli)
- Discussion (all participants)

Summary of the workshop

In this workshop, we aimed at further analysis of citizen science (CS) in social sciences and humanities (SSH). This workshop focused on discussing the concept, methods and existing practices of citizen science in SSH.

Egle Butkeviciene briefly presented decisions and outcomes from the previous workshop, that had been held in March, in Kaunas. The previous workshop aimed at improving our understanding of citizen science in SSH and set a target to develop a paper as an outcome of this COST activity.

The presentation also included discussion on SC as policy orientation, fuzzy barriers between concepts, open science & citizen science, different schemes of mapping CS (and in particular focusing on the one presented by Shirk et al (2012)¹), varieties of CS projects and methods used.

Dario Martinelli's part of the workshop explored the possibility of using humanities as an epistemological “added value” to the main paradigm of citizen science. The central idea is that humanities can be used for a critical approach to citizen science, and – most of all – to “account for the unaccountable”, that is, to attempt to categorize that part of the CS discourse based on individual, cultural, emotional and other factors that, due to its very nature, tends to escape “exact”, quantitative analysis. For this purpose, Martinelli employed, re-adapting them, two theories, borrowed from the areas of semiotics and multimodality studies respectively: Gino Stefani's model on “common competence” and Partn and Marler's model on redundancy and non-redundance in multimodal communication.

¹ Shirk, J. L., H. L. Ballard, C. C. Wilderman, T. Phillips, A. Wiggins, R. Jordan, E. McCallie, M. Minarchek, B. V. Lewenstein, M. E. Krasny, and R. Bonney. 2012. Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design. *Ecology and Society* 17 (2): 29. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5751/ES-04705-170229>

Decisions

1. To proceed with article development & provide comments and idea for its improvement;
2. Workshop participants, interested meaningfully contribute to the article development, should contact Egle Butkeviciene (by e-mail: egle.butkeviciene@ktu.lt) to be added to google docs working space.

Pictures

